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Tailoring the Chemistry and Morphology of Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotubes Forests, Implications for Smart Electrodes

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Vertically Aligned Carbon Nanotubes (VA-CNT)

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- Showcasing the outstanding properties of CNT has been cumbersome.
- VACNT architecture bypasses 2/3 'typical' CNT challenges.
- Key challenge: The delicate structure complicates solving the third

Property	Single-walled carbon nanotube	Double-walled carbon nanotube	Multiwalled carbon nanotube
Tensile strength (GPa)	50–100	23–63	10–60
Elastic modulus (TPa)	1	–	0.3–1
Elongation at break (%)	5.8	28	–
Density (g/cm ³)	1.3–1.5	1.5	1.8–2.0
Electric conductivity (S/m)	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶
Thermal conductivity at room temperature (W/m K)	6000	3000	2000

Motivation: VACNT-Hybrids

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- VACNT are very porous architectures (99vol% air), with immense surface-to-volume ratio
- For example: If a carbon nanotube has 10nm diameter and 2 mm length, aspect ratio will be $\sim 10^6$. In typical VACNT (1 cm² Si-die) there are $\sim 10^9$ CNT.
- Such conditions are 'prime real-estate' for secondary phases!

Strategy

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1. Protection of CNT Chemistry.

- Introduction of novel 'chemical' success criteria (proof: XPS).
- On top of existing 'structural' criteria (proof: Raman).

2. Retention of VACNT Architecture

- Morphological analysis (proof: SEM)
- Avoiding 'capillary forces' of wet methods.

3. Fabrication of VACNT-Hybrid

- Dry methods, such as sputtering and atomic layer deposition (ALD)

Air

Argon

O_2/Ar
Plasma

Controlled
Metal Melting

Metal Oxide
Coating

Methodology

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Scaffold Preparation

Water-assisted Chemical Vapor Deposition of VACNT

~1.8 nm Fe

~10 nm Al₂O₃

Si wafer

Interphase Engineering

Annealing at atmosphere of choice

Plasma treatment

<https://sinvacon.be/>

VACNT-Hybrid Composite Fabrication

(ALD) of Oxides

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Ostwald Ripening of Metals

Sputtering of gold

Characterization Techniques

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Basic “Toolkit” for the Surface Treating Engineer

Results - AuNP-beaded VACNT

- Higher temperatures create more spherical nanoparticles.

- At low temperature, we need time!

$$\text{MorphoJ sphericity} = \frac{V^2}{S^3} \cdot \frac{36}{\pi}$$

Results - Al₂O₃ coated nanotubes in VACNT

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Amorphous carbon plasma removal

Table 5. - Oxygen content and “π-π*” for VACNT arrays, for pristine and plasma-treated samples, at two different gas ratios, after 2.5 minutes of treatment.

	Pristine	O ₂ /Ar (3:3)	O ₂ /Ar (4:2)
Oxygen Center	0.50 (± 0.05)	8.47 (± 0.8)	1.66 (± 0.16)
Oxygen Periphery	2.85 (± 0.3)	15.55 (± 1.5)	19.93 (± 2)
“π-π*” Center	0.98 (± 0.1)	0.71 (± 0.07)	0.98 (± 0.1)
“π-π*” Periphery	0.91 (± 0.09)	0.59 (± 0.06)	0.47 (± 0.05)

Annealing atmosphere, choice 1 - Air

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Annealing atmosphere, choice 2 - Ar (Shir's and Ella's BSc project)

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Summary (To take home)

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- The electronic structure of MWCNT is conserved in post-treated VACNT, with clear validation criteria.
- VACNT high-interface hybrid structures are naturally inhomogeneous, and require a tailored surface treatment to ensure homogeneity.
- Lowering the fabrication temperature of VACNT-metal hybrids makes them more approachable for various applications (e.g. energy harvesting or bio-medical)